

Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility Services

Federated Road Design and Development for Optimal Operations

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Project Partners

FRODDO is a consortium of 19 key partners, including leading academic institutions, research organizations, and industry leaders from across Europe. The consortium includes:

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